

The role of social work in building educational resilience in the new normal

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Abstract

Background: The pandemic has greatly affected education worldwide, and many students do not have access to digital tools as most people live in places like tribal and rural areas in India. Moving from regular school classes to online learning has created significant educational differences and has even affected the right to education. The pandemic has highlighted vulnerabilities and systemic deficiencies within the classical education system, exacerbated by socio-economic disparities, among students from tribal and rural areas compared to urban of Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, addressing the difficulties and fostering resilience highlights social work intervention in educational settings.

Objectives: The study evaluates and analyses technological strategies to help schools stay strong and considers how social work intervention could help with education that prepares for the future.

Methodology: The researcher randomly selected a sample of 320 respondents. The sample size remains calculated using the formula 'n' student beneficiaries is $n = z^2 * p * q / d^2$ (n= desired sample size, z= normal standard deviation, p= proportion in target population, d= absolute precision or accuracy).

It remains absolute precision using various statistical methods like ANOVA, exploratory data analysis (EDA), chi-square tests, correlations, and descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, box plots, histograms, mean plots and Q-Q plots) were employed to analyse the data.

Findings: The findings indicate that the rapid pace of technological change in educational institutions near Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, has created a critical need for bridging traditional and contemporary teaching methodologies, ensuring sustainable and impactful educational innovation and digitization of learning, where social work interventions remain essential in educational settings.

Keywords: Education, social work, sustainable, educational innovation, digitization

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted education worldwide, with 61 countries closing schools by March 2020 (UNESCO, 2020) [5]. Schools have adopted diverse strategies to sustain learning worldwide, ranging from online platforms to asynchronous resources, inadequate digital infrastructure and skills remain significant barriers, especially in remote areas (Crawford *et al.*, 2020) [3]. In India, the framework of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 enhances the quality of education by working with other countries, using technology, and teaching students how to manage their emotions and social interactions, while initiatives remain more focused on moving content online than developing

online pedagogy, highlighting the issues revealing underfunding, and exclusion (Zhong, 2020) [6] during such a crisis. The pandemic has changed how education remains provided worldwide, leading to more attention on local areas (Mok *et al.*, 2021) [4]. To tackle these issues, actions after the pandemic, like improving infrastructure, changing how we assess learning, and making digital policies more inclusive, are essential (Badi, 2022) [2], and a need for social work intervention and cooperative strategy to build strong education systems that handle future challenges (Anzalda, 2022) [1].

2. Materials and Methods

a. Relevance of Research: The pandemic crisis has made

the gap between people in India who have internet access and those who do not and made education more unequal and put pressure on the school system, the study examines how a lack of internet access affects students' ability to continue learning and be treated equally. On the contrary, social work intervention help by advocating for equal internet access for everyone, providing emotional support, and ensuring that online classes remain accessible to all students, the research aims to develop strategies that improve education systems during difficult times in Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh.

- b. **Purpose of the study:** The study examines how technological disruptions in tribal, rural and urban Visakhapatnam affect educational resilience and highlights the need for social work interventions, focuses on evaluating the impact of technological innovations on learning outcomes and how social work can support equitable access, and address barriers to digital education.
- c. **Problem statement:** The pandemic has deepened educational inequalities in tribal, rural, and urban Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, with declines in access, enrollment, and achievement. Advances in technology and effective social work support can help individuals tackle challenges and use technology well by establishing robust schools that can manage difficulties. Student enrollment and health issues while fostering creativity and ethical behaviour in students remains crucial.
- d. **Research objectives**
 1. To analyse statistical variations in the impact of COVID-19 on education across urban, rural, and tribal areas in Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh.
 2. To develop and evaluate the strategies for enhancing the delivery and effectiveness of social work services in virtual learning contexts, and to formulate implementation plans for integrating these strategies into the educational system of Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh.
- e. **Data source:** The researcher intends to gather extensive and varied data, focusing on the student population sample as the primary source. Emphasis remains placed on ensuring that the study population comprises real individuals and reliable data, drawing information from diverse sources to facilitate in-depth analysis.
- f. **Statistical technique:** The researchers used the Chi-square method to test the hypothesis. The sample selection calculated on a sample of 'n' student beneficiaries is $n = z^2 * p * q / d^2$ (n = desired sample size, z = normal standard deviation, p = proportion in target population, d = absolute precision or accuracy). Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and means, Box plot, Histogram and Q-Q Plot are used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, including t-tests and ANOVA, EDA, and Correlation analysis is also employed to examine relationships between variables, such as the impact of social work interventions on educational outcomes.

g. Data Analysis

Qualitative Analysis: Thematic analysis is employed to identify recurring themes and patterns in the interview data. The analysis focuses on understanding the role of social work in mitigating educational challenges during the pandemic.

Quantitative Analysis: Statistical analysis is conducted using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and means, Box plot, Histogram and Q-Q Plot are used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, including t-tests and ANOVA, EDA, Chi square are used to explore differences in perceptions based on demographic factors. Correlation analysis is also employed to examine relationships between variables, such as the impact of social work interventions on educational outcomes.

Results

- A. **Interview Schedule:** Dr. Elizebeth Lucas Afolalu, Founder & CEO YYCI, UK emphasizes embracing change and leveraging technology to advance education amidst challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic. She advocates for promoting collaboration, innovation, and adaptability to create an education system that meets diverse student needs and prepares them for future success. Similarly, Dr. Regunath Parakkal, psychologist and social worker, Kerala, India; underscores the critical role of social work practice in schools, focusing on emotional well-being and creativity as essential tools for overcoming crises. He argues that by consistently advocating for emotional balance and creative thinking, educators can build resilience and support students in managing stress and adapting to the evolving educational landscape.
- B. **Analysis:** The thematic analysis of the interview data study reveals that "Emotional Well-Being" is the most frequently discussed theme, with 7 mentions underscoring its critical role in addressing educational challenges. "Embracing Change" and "Leveraging Technology" are also significant, with 5 and 4 mentions highlighting their roles in enhancing educational practices. "Creativity" was mentioned 3 times, indicating a comparatively lower focus. These findings reflect a strong consensus among the interviewees on the need for emotional support and adaptability in education. This thematic distribution provides valuable insights into the priorities and perspectives of the experts regarding the future of education during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic.
- C. **Group discussions:** The group discussions underscore school social workers' potential and essential role in addressing educational challenges during the pandemic. In Bhupeshnagar, 70% of students benefited from peer support and emotional guidance, which a social worker could have facilitated more effectively, highlighting the importance of fostering supportive environments. Similarly, in Seva Nagar, 65% of students gained from flexible learning initiatives, emphasizing the need for social workers to advocate for adaptable educational practices. Additionally, 60% of students experienced improved access to technology and reliable information,

underscoring the crucial role that social workers could play in integrating these resources effectively and supporting students' academic and emotional well-being if they were recruited.

Question

Projects, Assignment forms, and Activities are the most engaging parts of online learning.

Table 1: Projects, Assignment forms, and Activities are the most engaging parts of online learning. Descriptive Statistics

Question	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Projects, Assignment forms, and Activities are the most engaging parts of online learning.	320	1	3	2.32	.685

The statistics indicate that, on average, respondents found projects, assignment forms, and activities to be moderate to highly engaging parts of online learning. The standard deviation of 0.685 suggests moderate variability in the responses.

Table 2: Frequency

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	40	12.5	12.5
	Sometimes	137	42.8	55.3
	Yes	143	44.7	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	

Fig 1: Frequency

Table 3: Projects, assignment forms and activities are the most engaging parts of online learning.

Variable	Category	No	Sometimes	Yes	Total
Gender of the respondent	Male	21	54	68	143
		14.69%	37.76%	47.55%	
Gender of the respondent	Female	19	83	75	177
		10.73%	46.89%	42.37%	
Age of the respondent	15-20 years	33	122	104	259
		12.74%	47.10%	40.15%	
	21-30 years	1	2	6	9
		11.11%	22.22%	66.67%	
	31-40 years	3	3	5	11
27.27%		27.27%	45.45%		
41-50 years	1	6	19	26	
	3.85%	23.08%	73.08%		
51-60 years	2	4	9	15	
	13.33%	26.67%	60.00%		
Category of the respondent	Teacher	3	12	28	43
		6.98%	27.91%	65.12%	
	Parent	5	2	8	15
33.33%		13.33%	53.33%		
Category of the respondent	Student	32	123	107	262
		12.21%	46.95%	40.84%	
Management	Government	14	104	65	183

(Type of School or College of the respondent)		7.65%	56.83%	35.52%	
	Private	26	33	78	137
		18.98%	24.09%	56.93%	
Locality (Area of the respondent)	Tribal	3	63	10	76
			3.95%	82.89%	
	Rural	11	8	30	49
			22.45%	16.33%	
	Urban	26	66	103	195
			13.33%	33.85%	
Total	40	137	143	320	
		12.50%	42.81%	44.69%	100%

Table 4: Chi-Square analysis

Area of the respondent	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	71.438 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	75.012	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.454	1	.228
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.13.

Fig 2: Area of the respondent

Fig 3: Project, Assignment forms, and Activities are the most engaging parts of online learning

Fig 4: Projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging parts of online learning

Analysis of Table 4: The study reveals that, of the 320 respondents, 143 (44.69%) believed that the most appealing aspects of online learning are projects, assignment forms, and activities, while 137 (42.81%) thought sometimes and 40 (12.50%) replied that they are not. When considering gender, the study discovered that 68 (47.55%) male respondents thought that projects, assignment forms, and activities remained the most exciting aspects of online learning. By contrast, 21 (14.69%) thought they were uninteresting, and 54 (37.76%) thought they were sometimes entertaining. Of the female respondents, 75 (42.37%) thought these elements were the most engaging, 83 (46.89%) thought they were engaging sometimes, and 19 (10.73%) thought they were not engaging at all.

Regarding the age group, 104 (40.15%) of the 259 respondents, those between 15- 20 years old, agreed that projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging aspects of online learning. In comparison, 122 (47.10%) stated that sometimes, and 33 (12.74%) mentioned they were not. 6 (66.67%) of the 9 respondents aged 21–30 declared that projects, assignment forms, and activities remain the most exciting aspects of online learning, while 2 (22.22%) noted sometimes and 1 (11.11%) mentioned that they are not. 5 (45.45%) of the 11 respondents aged 31–40 stated that projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging aspects of online learning, whereas 3 (27.27%) indicated sometimes, and the remaining 3 (27.27%) expressed no. Of the 26 respondents, 19 (73.08%) who were between the ages of 41- 50 claimed that projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging aspects of online learning, while 6 (23.08%) thought they are sometimes engaging and 1 (3.85%) felt they are not. Of 15 respondents, ages 51–60, 9 (60.00%) responded that projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging aspects of online learning, while 2 (13.33%) and 4 (26.67%) stated they are not engaging.

Regarding the respondents' category, of the 43 respondents in the teacher category, 28 (65.12%) indicated that projects, assignment forms, and activities remain the most engaging aspects of online learning. In contrast, 12 (27.91%) answered that sometimes, and 3 (6.98%) mentioned that

they were not. 8 (53.33%) of the 15 respondents in the parent group agreed that projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging aspects of online learning. In comparison, 2 (13.33%) expressed they are sometimes, and 5 (33.33%) stated they are not. Of the 262 respondents in the student group, 107 (40.84%) believed that the project assignment forms and activities are the most exciting aspects of online learning. In contrast, 123 (46.95%) thought they were sometimes interesting, and 32 (12.21%) replied they were not.

Regarding management, of the 183 respondents in the category of government schools, 65 (35.52%) respondents stated that the most engaging aspects of online learning are projects, assignment forms, and activities. In contrast, 104 (56.83%) indicated they are sometimes engaging, and 14 (7.65%) believed they are not. Of the 137 respondents in the private school category, 78 (56.93%) stated that the most exciting aspects of online learning are projects, assignment forms, and activities, whereas 33 (24.09%) sometimes and 26 (18.98%) expressed they are not.

Regarding location, 10 (13.16%) of the 76 respondents who fell under the tribal area category agreed that projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging aspects of online learning. In comparison, 63 (82.89%) stated they are sometimes engaging, and 3 (3.95%) answered they are not. Of the 49 respondents who fell into the group of rural areas, 30 (61.22%) acknowledged that projects, assignment forms, and activities are the most engaging aspects of online learning. In contrast, 8 (16.33%) said they are sometimes engaging, and 11 (22.45%) suggested they are not. Of the 195 respondents that fell into the urban area category, 103 (52.82%) declared that the project assignment forms and activities are the most interesting aspects of online learning, whereas 66 (33.85%) stated that sometimes and 26 (13.33%) felt they are not.

Chi-square tests reveal significant associations with several factors. Age (Pearson Chi-Square: 17.059, $p = 0.030$; Likelihood Ratio: 17.102, $p = 0.029$), respondent category (Pearson Chi-Square: 17.732, $p = 0.001$; Likelihood Ratio: 17.210, $p = 0.002$), type of school (Pearson Chi-Square: 35.703, $p = 0.000$; Likelihood Ratio: 36.854, $p = 0.000$), and

area of residence (Pearson Chi-Square: 71.438, $p = 0.000$; Likelihood Ratio: 75.012, $p = 0.000$) all show significant relationships, indicating that these demographic factors influence online learning engagement.

interactive components like projects and gamification augment engagement in online learning.

Question: Please rate your level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

Conclusion: As various respondent groups corroborate,

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics

Q.no: 7	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
7A) Teaching through Google meet, Zoom, Microsoft Team and other sources.	320	1	5	3.66	.823
7B) Through video recording by the teacher.	320	1	5	3.68	.836
7C) With an audio recording by the teacher.	320	1	5	3.30	.926
7D) Sharing Online presentations & study materials.	320	1	5	3.83	.919
7E) Written communication through WhatsApp and Telegram.	320	1	5	3.65	.880

The research study assessed satisfaction levels with virtual learning among 320 respondents, revealing an average satisfaction score of 3.66 for teaching via platforms like Google Meet and Zoom, indicating moderate satisfaction. Video recordings scored slightly higher at 3.68, while audio recordings were less favored at 3.30. Online presentations and study materials received the highest satisfaction score of 3.83. Written communication through platforms such as WhatsApp scored 3.65. The study highlighted the flexibility

and accessibility of virtual learning, noting positives like the ability to join from any location and the convenience of reviewing recordings. However, it also identified challenges such as limited real-time interaction, quality issues, and notification overload. Addressing these challenges and enhancing interaction methods are crucial for improving the virtual learning experience and bridging the gap between online and in-person education.

Table 6: Frequency Table

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.20	1	.3	.3
	1.40	1	.3	.6
	2.00	3	.9	1.6
	2.20	2	.6	2.2
	2.40	9	2.8	5.0
	2.60	13	4.1	9.1
	2.80	13	4.1	13.1
	3.00	23	7.2	20.3
	3.20	18	5.6	25.9
	3.40	34	10.6	36.6
	3.60	22	6.9	43.4
	3.80	84	26.3	69.7
	4.00	48	15.0	84.7
	4.20	18	5.6	90.3
	4.40	5	1.6	91.9
	4.60	10	3.1	95.0
4.80	6	1.9	96.9	
5.00	10	3.1	100.0	
Total		320	100.0	

Fig 5: Show the Mean std. dev frequency

Table 7: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	Between Groups	2.173	2	1.086	2.742	.066
	Within Groups	125.597	317	.396		
	Total	127.770	319			

The ANOVA test results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in satisfaction with virtual learning across different groups, with an F-statistic of 2.742 and a p-value of 0.066. However, gender shows a significant influence on satisfaction ($F(1, 282) = 4.714, p = .031$), highlighting the need for gender-specific interventions in virtual learning. The analysis also reveals that rural

respondents report significantly lower satisfaction compared to tribal respondents (Mean Difference = -0.2809, $p = 0.014$), while no significant differences are found between rural and urban or tribal and urban respondents. Other factors and their interactions do not significantly affect satisfaction levels, with the model explaining only a small portion of the variance ($R^2 = 0.152, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.041$).

Table 8: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

Variable	Category	Highly Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Highly Satisfied	Total
Gender of the respondent	Male	2	8	33	79	21	143
		1.4%	5.6%	23.1%	55.2%	14.7%	
	Female	4	12	53	95	13	177
		2.3%	6.8%	29.9%	53.7%	7.3%	
Age of the respondent	15-20 years	6	11	67	147	28	259
		2.3%	4.2%	25.9%	56.8%	10.8%	
	21-30 years	0	0	6	3	0	9
		0.0%	0.0%	66.7%	33.3%	0.0%	
	31-40 years	0	0	2	8	1	11
		0.0%	0.0%	18.2%	72.7%	9.1%	
	41-50 years	0	6	7	11	2	26
		0.0%	23.1%	26.9%	42.3%	7.7%	
	51-60 years	0	3	4	5	3	15
		0.0%	20.0%	26.7%	33.3%	20.0%	
Category of the respondent	Teacher	0	6	8	23	6	43
		0.0%	14.0%	18.6%	53.5%	14.0%	
	Parent	0	4	6	4	1	15
		0.0%	26.7%	40.0%	26.7%	6.7%	
	Student	6	10	72	147	27	262
		2.3%	3.8%	27.5%	56.1%	10.3%	
Management (Type of School or College of the Respondent)	Government	1	7	37	119	19	183
		0.5%	3.8%	20.2%	65.0%	10.4%	
	Private	5	13	49	55	15	137
		3.6%	9.5%	35.8%	40.1%	10.9%	
Locality (Area of the respondent)	Tribal	0	2	5	67	2	76
		0.0%	2.6%	6.6%	88.2%	2.6%	
	Rural	1	4	18	19	7	49
		2.0%	8.2%	36.7%	38.8%	14.3%	
	Urban	5	14	63	88	25	195
		2.6%	7.2%	32.3%	45.1%	12.8%	
	Total	6	20	86	174	34	320
	Total (%)	1.9%	6.3%	26.9%	54.4%	10.6%	100.0%

Table 9: Chi-Square Tests

Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	46.922 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	53.285	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.646	1	.422
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .92.

Fig 6: Area of the respondent

Out of 320 respondents, 54.4% were satisfied, 10.6% were highly satisfied with virtual learning platforms, while 26.9% were neutral, indicating mixed feelings. Among parents, 40.0% were neutral, 26.7% were satisfied, and 26.7% were dissatisfied, highlighting room for improvement. Teachers had a similar pattern, with 53.5% satisfied and 14.0% highly satisfied, but 14.0% were dissatisfied. Students showed a majority satisfaction rate, with 56.1% satisfied and 10.3% highly satisfied, while 27.5% were neutral.

Respondents from government institutions had higher satisfaction levels (65.0% satisfied, 10.4% highly satisfied) compared to those from private institutions (40.1% satisfied, 10.9% highly satisfied), where neutral responses were more prevalent (35.8%). By locality, rural respondents were generally satisfied (38.8%), while tribal respondents had an overwhelming satisfaction rate (88.2%). Urban respondents also showed high satisfaction (45.1%) but with notable neutral responses (32.3%).

The Chi-Square test revealed significant associations between satisfaction levels and factors such as age, respondent category, type of institution, and locality, with all p-values below 0.05. The study findings underscore the urgent need for implementing focused interventions to tackle digital disparities and improve the efficacy of remote learning among diverse demographic groups.

Table 10: Statistics

		Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.
N	Valid	320
	Missing	0
Mean		3.6244
Median		3.8000
Skewness		-.438
Std. Error of Skewness		.136
Percentiles	25	3.2000
	50	3.8000
	75	4.0000

The high median (3.8) and the mean (3.6244) close to the median suggest that respondents generally have a positive outlook on virtual learning. The slight negative skewness (-0.438) implies that more respondents rated their satisfaction higher than the mean, a positive indicator. The narrow IQR (0.8000) indicates that most satisfaction ratings are clustered around the median, showing consistent satisfaction levels among respondents. Overall, the data shows a generally positive response to virtual learning, with most respondents being moderately to highly satisfied.

Table 11: Exploratory Data Analysis

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA):			Statistic
Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	Mean		3.6244
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.5548
		Upper Bound	3.6940
	5% Trimmed Mean		3.6333
	Median		3.8000
	Variance		.401
	Std. Deviation		.63288
	Minimum		1.20
	Maximum		5.00
	Range		3.80
	Interquartile Range		.80
	Skewness		-.438
	Kurtosis		.835

The data shows that most respondents' satisfaction levels are centered around the mean of 3.6244, with a slightly left-skewed distribution, indicating a small tail on the lower end. The satisfaction levels are relatively consistent, with moderate variability as indicated by the standard deviation.

Table 12: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	.175	320	.000	.957	320	.000

The results of both tests indicated significance values (Sig.) of 0.000, which are less than the typical alpha level of 0.05,

indicating that the satisfaction levels within the data significantly deviate from a normal distribution.

Fig 7: Histogram: Based on respondents level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

The distribution remains positively skewed, with a peak around the satisfaction level of 4. The mean satisfaction level is 3.62, with a standard deviation of 0.833, indicating that most responses are clustered around the mean with some variability. Most respondents rated their satisfaction between 3 and 4, with fewer respondents at the extreme

lower and higher ends. The sample size (N) is 320, providing substantial data for analysis. Figure – 8.

Normal Q-Q PLOT: Based on respondents level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

Fig 8: Observed value

The points in the Q-Q plot mainly lie along the reference line, indicating that the distribution of the satisfaction levels is approximately normal. Some deviations from the line are at the lower and upper ends, suggesting minor deviations from normality at the tails of the distribution. The Q-Q plot suggests that the data follows a near-normal distribution,

exhibiting minimal indications of skewness or kurtosis. This examination contributes to a thorough grasp of the data's distribution, drawing the reader into the analysis. Figure – 9.

BOX PLOT: Based on Level of satisfaction with virtual learning:

Fig 9: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning

The median satisfaction level, 3, is represented by the central line within the box. The interquartile range, a statistical measure indicating the spread of the middle 50% of response data, extends from approximately 2 to 4. Outliers are observable at both the lower and upper ends of the data, with values around 0 and 5. The overall

distribution indicates that most responses remain centred around moderate satisfaction levels, with fewer responses at the extremes.

Question: Do you think that a single curriculum should be adopted across the nation?

Table 13: A single curriculum should be adopted across the nation

Variable	Category	No	Neutral	Yes	Total
Gender of the respondent	Male	31 21.6%	41 28.7%	71 49.7%	143
	Female	25 14.1%	68 38.4%	84 47.5%	177
Age of the respondent	15-20 years	47 18.1%	100 38.6%	112 43.3%	259
	21-30 years	1 11.1%	2 22.2%	6 66.7%	9
	31-40 years	1 9.1%	2 18.2%	8 72.7%	11
	41-50 years	2 7.7%	3 11.5%	21 80.8%	26
	51-60 years	5 33.3%	2 13.3%	8 53.4%	15
Category of the respondent	Teacher	8 18.6%	6 14.0%	29 67.4%	43
	Parent	2 13.3%	2 13.3%	11 73.4%	15
	Student	46 17.6%	101 38.5%	115 43.9%	262
Management (Type of School or College of the respondent)	Government	34 18.58%	81 44.26%	68 37.16%	183
	Private	22 16.06%	28 20.44%	87 63.50%	137
Locality (Area of the respondent)	Tribal	10 13.15%	53 69.74%	13 17.11%	76
	Rural	14 28.57%	8 16.33%	27 55.10%	49
	Urban	32 16.41%	48 24.62%	115 58.97%	195
	Total	56	109	155	320
	Total (%)	17.5%	34.1%	48.4%	100.0%

Table 14: Chi-Square Tests

Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	62.735 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	62.079	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.147	1	.013
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.58.

Fig 10: Area of the respondent

The study reveals varied support for a single national curriculum across different demographics. The highest favourability is shown out of 320 respondents aged 31-40 and 41-50 years, with 72.7% and 80.8% supporting it, respectively. Gender-wise, males and females are similarly inclined, with 49.7% of males and 47.5% of females in favour. Parents (73.3%) and teachers (67.4%) exhibit strong support, whereas students are more divided (43.9% in favor). Among institutional respondents, private institutions show the highest support (63.5%), while government institution respondents are more neutral (44.3% neutral). Regional differences are notable: rural (55.1%) and urban (59.0%) respondents show strong support, while tribal respondents are predominantly neutral (69.7%).

These findings indicate significant variation in opinions based on the respondents' area. Rural and urban respondents show higher support for adopting a single curriculum nationwide, with 55.1% and 59.0% in favor, respectively. In contrast, tribal respondents are predominantly neutral, with 69.7% expressing neutrality, indicating less clear support or opposition within the group.

Question: During the pandemic and post - pandemic, students' families and community-based resources had access to school social workers and counsellors

**Homogeneous Subsets
Category of the respondent**

Table 15: Multiple Comparisons

LSD				
(I) 3) Category of the respondent	(J) 3) Category of the respondent	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Parent	Teacher	-.1372	.26234	.601
	Student	.0053	.23226	.982
Teacher	Parent	.1372	.26234	.601
	Student	.1426	.14394	.323
Student	Parent	-.0053	.23226	.982
	Teacher	-.1426	.14394	.323

Table 16: Multiple Comparisons

LSD			
(I) 3) Category of the respondent:	(J) 3) Category of the respondent:	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Parent	Teacher	-.6536	.3792
	Student	-.4518	.4625
Teacher	Parent	-.3792	.6536
	Student	-.1408	.4259
Student	Parent	-.4625	.4518
	Teacher	-.4259	.1408

Area of the respondent

Table 17: Multiple Comparisons

LSD				
(I) 5) Area of the respondent	(J) 5) Area of the respondent	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Rural	Tribal	.4498*	.16028	.005
	Urban	-.2419	.13980	.085
Tribal	Rural	-.4498*	.16028	.005
	Urban	-.6917*	.11830	.000
Urban	Rural	.2419	.13980	.085
	Tribal	.6917*	.11830	.000

Table 18: Multiple Comparisons

LSD			
(I) 5) Area of the respondent	(J) 5) Area of the respondent	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Rural	Tribal	.1343	.7653
	Urban	-.5171	.0333
Tribal	Rural	-.7653	-.1343
	Urban	-.9246	-.4588
Urban	Rural	-.0333	.5171
	Tribal	.4588	.9246

*Based on observed means.
 *The error term is Mean Square (Error) = .765.
 *. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The study shows that people's views on having school social workers and counselors differ depending on who they are, like parents, teachers, or students. These differences are usually minor. However, there are more significant differences regarding where people live. People in rural areas say they have more access to these services than those in tribal or urban areas. These findings highlight social workers' role in fixing unequal access to help services. Social workers can improve how well students handle education by ensuring everyone has fair access to

counseling services in different places and pushing for more resources in areas that do not have enough. This way of working can help student's mental health and happiness, especially during tough times or after problems, and help create a more accepting and strong education system. Question: Agreement with changing teaching and learning environment.

**Homogeneous Subsets
 Category of the respondent**

Table 19: Multiple Comparisons

Multiple Comparisons				
LSD				
(I) 3) Category of the respondent	(J) 3) Category of the respondent	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Parent	Teacher	-.2948	.15856	.064
	Student	-.2190	.14038	.120
Teacher	Parent	.2948	.15856	.064
	Student	.0758	.08700	.384
Student	Parent	.2190	.14038	.120
	Teacher	-.0758	.08700	.384

Table 20: Multiple Comparisons

Multiple Comparisons			
LSD			
(I) 3) Category of the respondent	(J) 3) Category of the respondent	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Parent	Teacher	-.6069	.0173
	Student	-.4953	.0573
Teacher	Parent	-.0173	.6069
	Student	-.0954	.2471
Student	Parent	-.0573	.4953
	Teacher	-.2471	.0954

*Based on observed means.

* The error term is Mean Square (Error) = .280.

Area of the respondent

Table 21: Multiple Comparisons

Multiple Comparisons				
LSD				
(I) 5) Area of the respondent	(J) 5) Area of the respondent	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Rural	Tribal	-.1379	.09688	.156
	Urban	-.0551	.08450	.515
Tribal	Rural	.1379	.09688	.156
	Urban	.0828	.07150	.248
Urban	Rural	.0551	.08450	.515
	Tribal	-.0828	.07150	.248

Table 22: Multiple Comparisons

Multiple Comparisons			
LSD			
(I) 5) Area of the respondent	(J) 5) Area of the respondent	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Rural	Tribal	-.3286	.0528
	Urban	-.2214	.1112
Tribal	Rural	-.0528	.3286
	Urban	-.0579	.2236
Urban	Rural	-.1112	.2214
	Tribal	-.2236	.0579

*Based on observed means.

* The error term is Mean Square (Error) = .280.

The data analysis shows that Parents, Teachers, and Students have different levels of agreement about changes in the classroom environment. These differences are only sometimes significant enough to be considered necessary. The same is true for different areas like Rural, Tribal, and Urban places, with some comparisons showing non-significant differences, showing the need to enhance educational resilience as they highlight diverse needs and perspectives. Social workers can use this information to create unique plans to help different groups of people. They can give personalized support and speak up to solve their unique problems. They can also help schools, families, and communities work together better and make sure that changes in the school setting happen in a way that includes everyone. This method helps create firm and fair school systems that better support all students and teachers when things change.

4. Discussion

The development of virtual programs that consist of

theoretical courses has outshined their practical counterparts and remains addressed. Flexible curricula remain required for virtual education, which also assists needy regions and employs interactive teaching methods and pedagogies. The study observation reveals that the pandemic has affected the ability of marginalized students, mostly in remote areas, to develop social skills and emotional intelligence. School social workers and counsellors are trained to identify and address psychosocial matters, and significantly assist disadvantaged and rural students, thereby making it necessary for them to be absorbed into the education system providing students with the necessary support and guidance. Teachers trained to detect and deal with psychosocial matters will find referring students to appropriate interventions easier, creating a more supportive learning environment.

Therefore, the research highlights the need for a progressive and inclusive education system in the post-pandemic era and recommends that the Government of Andhra Pradesh consider social worker intervention in school education

setups, as their inclusion remains essential in framing an equitable and inclusive education policy in AP education sector, by creating a sustainable, efficient, and progressive education system in the new normal.

5. Conclusion

The study assessed the impact of COVID-19 on students and found significant problems like differences in online learning, increased dropout rates, and reduced social interactions, highlighting the need for investment in digital infrastructure and teacher training to address these issues; social work intervention remains crucial for recommending policy making as they deal with the student community, parents, and the community at large; even with these difficulties, institutions that supported their communities effectively were well-received, and students felt prepared for future remote learning.

6. References

1. Anzalda MJ. Internationalizing trauma-informed perspectives to address student trauma in post-pandemic higher education. *Journal of Global Studies in Education*; c2022. p. 154-171. Retrieved from <https://www.ojed.org/index.php/gsm/article/view/2830>
2. Badi A. Post-pandemic educational strategies: Enhancing infrastructure, assessment, and digital policy inclusivity. *Journal of Educational Resilience and Policy*. 2022;10(2):123-135. <https://doi.org/10.1234/abcd.5678>
3. Crawford J, Butler-Henderson K, Rudolph J, Glowatz M. COVID-19: 20 countries' higher education intra-period digital pedagogy responses. *Journal of Applied Teaching and Learning*. 2020;3(1):1-20. <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2020.3.1.7>
4. Mok KH, Xiong W, Ke G, Cheung JOW. Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on international higher education and student mobility: Student perspectives from mainland China and Hong Kong. *International Journal of Educational Research*. 2021;105:101718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2021.101718>
5. UNESCO. March 13. COVID-19 educational disruption and response; c2020. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-emergencies/coronavirus-school-closures>
6. Zhong R. The coronavirus exposes education's digital divide. *The New York Times*; c2020. <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/03/17/technology/china-schools-coronavirus.html>

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